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REPORT 4

TURNEYES STUDY 2:
PUNITIVENESS

November 2024

The project Turning a Blind Eye to Scandal has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 892951

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Turning a Blind Eye to Scandal

Study 2: Punitiveness

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& David Redlawsk

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 892951

The data collection was funded by the University of Delaware.

A version of this report has been published

Redlawsk, D. P., & Walter, A. S. (2024). Partisan Differences in Voters’ Desire for Punishment in Response to Politicians’ Moral Transgressions. *American Politics Research*, 52(6), 611-623. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1532673X241263086>

While a politician who commits a moral transgression can be negatively affected at the polls in either an election or re-election bid, the magnitude of the loss of electoral support is generally small and often insufficient to prevent victory, especially for incumbents (Praino & Stockemer, 2021; Riera et al., 2013; Brown, 2006; Kauder & Potrafke, 2016; Basinger, 2013; Banducci & Karp, 1994). The electoral consequences for political candidates and parties in the aftermath of morally transgressive behavior seem limited. At the same time, there is considerable heterogeneity in how and whether political candidates and parties are held accountable (Riera et al., 2013; Kauder & Potrafke, 2016; Brown, 2006) with not all voters equally likely to desire accountability (Alexander, Bågenholm & Charron, 2020; Riera et al., 2013; Saxton & Barnes, 2022). Voters give varying weights to moral transgressions in their vote decisions (Riera et al., 2013). Some research suggests that women, conservatives, unsophisticated, and voters most financially affected are more likely to hold moral transgressors electorally accountable (Alexander, Bågenholm & Charron, 2020; Riera et al., 2013; Fernández-Vázquez, Barberá, & Rivero; Dimock & Jacobson, 1995; Saxton & Barnes, 2022). Failures of electoral punishment challenge democratic accountability, a core tenet of representative democracy.

Although voters may not always hold politicians electorally accountable, this does not mean they care little about moral misconduct. The vote decision is based on many criteria (Funck & McCabe, 2020) including having a viable alternative candidate from which to choose. As a result, moral misconduct may not be at the top of people's minds in every case. Nonetheless, it is important to better understand voter responses to such misconduct. To do so, we argue it is worthwhile to take a step back and examine punitiveness, i.e. people's intuitive desire for moral punishment (Hoffman et al., 2018). A desire for punishment is a necessary precursor to holding politicians' electorally accountable. Examining voters' desire

for punishment outside of the electoral context will show the extent voter heterogeneity in electoral response is already present in behavioral intentions for punishment before votes are cast. Heterogeneity in people's punitive responses can only be partially explained by differences in the events experienced or witnessed; there are also differences in the levels of punitiveness across individuals and how readily they can be provoked to punish moral wrongdoing. Research has shown this to be the case for people's responses to everyday life transgressions (Hoffman et al., 2018) and we have no reason to expect this to differ for peoples' responses to moral transgressions by politicians.

Outside the context of war and conflict, political scientists have paid surprisingly little attention to individual differences in punitiveness in response to politicians' moral transgressions. While notable exceptions include Ashokkumar, Galaif & Swann, Jr., (2019), Halmburger, et al. (2012), and Filindra & Harbridge-Yong (2022), none of these studies investigated partisan differences in punitiveness. There are a few studies that report partisan differences in other responses (such as emotional reactions) to politicians committing moral transgressions (Wolsky, 2022; Walter & Redlawsk, 2019; 2021), but no other work has focused on punitiveness, to our knowledge. To address this gap, we examine whether U.S. partisan voters differ in punitiveness in response to politicians' moral violations and whether these differences persist when controlling for voters' perceptions of the severity of moral violations.

We conduct a survey-embedded vignette study in which we expose respondents to a randomly selected vignette describing a politician committing a moral or social transgression. Within the vignette, we manipulate the partisanship of the transgressor (Democrat/Republican/no partisanship mentioned) and the type of transgression using the five moral principles described by Moral Foundation Theory (Graham et al., 2011), i.e. violation of Care, Fairness, Loyalty, Authority and Sanctity. We added a social norm

transgression to provide a potential baseline case. A total of 2997 U. S. respondents participated in this study between October 2 and November 3, 2020, as the U.S. Presidential election was underway. In this paper our primary focus is on partisan voters exposed to the moral vignettes, rather than the social norm, giving us a total of 2076 respondents.

We find that partisan voters differ in their desire for punishment in response to politicians' moral transgressions. When voters perceive the severity of the moral violation committed to be low, Republicans have a stronger desire to punish than do Democrats. However, Republicans' levels of punitiveness depend on the partisanship of the transgressor, with much less willingness to punish in-party transgressors. We do not find a similar effect for Democratic voters at low levels of severity. However, when voters perceive the severity of the moral transgression to be moderate or high, Democrats have a stronger desire to punish the transgressing politician than do Republicans. However, regardless of the level of perceived severity of the moral transgression, Democrats show no in-party bias in their desire to punish. Our findings suggest that partisan voters are heterogeneous in punitiveness, but this relationship is strongly mediated by perceived severity. In addition, at the time of this study, Republicans and Democrats differed in how severe they perceived politicians' immoral behaviour and whether a transgressor should be punished. This study shows the importance of considering punitiveness when trying to solve the puzzle of voters' heterogeneous electoral responses to politicians' moral transgressions. More broadly this study also contributes to our understanding of group bias in punitiveness.

The rest of this paper proceeds as follows. First, we discuss the punitiveness literature and its implications for politicians involved in moral transgressions. Second, we discuss our data collection and analysis strategy. Third, we present the results, and finally, we draw conclusions and suggest limitations and avenues for further research.

Individual Differences in Punitiveness

We focus on voters' punitiveness, i.e. an intuitive desire for moral punishment (Hoffman et al., 2018) in response to politicians' violations of principles of right and wrong. Such moral transgressions can be precursors to political scandals, which are "actions or events involving certain kinds of transgressions which become known to others and are sufficiently serious to elicit a public response" (Thompson, 2000:13). In general, some desire for moral punishment is universal (Hoffman et al., 2018; Heffner & Feldman Hall, 2019) and is generally motivated by goals to prevent future wrongdoing, restoration of the wrongdoing, and/or reformation of the offender (Hoffman et al. 2018). Punishment is essential to maintaining and reinforcing moral systems (Hoffman et al., 2018) and the desire to punish is more the result of an intuitive than a reasoned process (Darley, 2009; Van Prooijen, 2017; Haidt, 2001).

Individuals differ in their levels of desire for moral punishment (Hoffman et al., 2018; Carroll et al., 1987). These differences can stem from the context of the violation – including who the victims are and the involvement of any third parties not directly harmed by the transgression (Heffner & Feldman Hall, 2019). Since normally most voters are not directly harmed by politicians' moral transgressions, we focus here on third party judgment, the desire to inflict moral punishment on those who have harmed someone else (Yudkin et al., 2016), examining how voters' own partisan identities, the shared partisan identity between voters and politicians, and the perceived severity of the offense help explain heterogeneity in desire for punishing morally transgressive politicians.

People can have multiple social identities, the subjective sense of belonging to a group (Tajfel, 1981). The social identity of primary importance for responses to politicians' moral transgressions is partisanship (e.g. Wolsky, 2022; Walter & Redlawsk, 2019; 2021; Bhatti et al. 2013). As with so much in voting behaviour, we expect partisan identity to

influence desires to punish politicians, both in terms of in- and out-party politicians as well as in terms of the perceived severity of different types of moral transgressions and overall desire for punishment.

Hypotheses

As noted earlier, punitiveness has not been examined much by political scientists, with the exception of the field of war and conflict studies (see for instance work on voters' attitudes of military punishment of interstate aggression, such as Liberman, 2007, 2013, 2014). Accordingly, we also draw on research from the field of criminal punishment in developing our hypotheses. Various studies in that field suggest to us that Republicans should be more punitive than Democrats. Republicans are more likely to support severe interrogation techniques of terrorist suspects, including torture (Carlsmith & Sood, 2009; Lieberman, 2013; 2014), stricter laws (Michel & Bardeen 2019), tougher prison sentences (King & Wheelock, 2007), adult death penalty (Michel & Bardeen, 2019; King & Wheelock, 2007; Cochran, Boots & Chamlin, 2006), and the use of deadly force by the police (Michel & Bardeen, 2019). Cochran, Boots & Chamlin (2006) and Jacobs & Carmichael (2004) argue that Republicans have a stronger desire to punish than Democrats as they are more inclined to dispositional attribution styles which hold individuals rather than situational or environmental influences responsible for their misconduct. Partisan differences in punitiveness might also reflect ideological differences (Lieberman 2007), as research has consistently linked punitiveness to conservatism, with conservatives exhibiting higher levels of punitiveness than liberals (Baker & Booth, 2016; Hofmann et al., 2018; Jacobs & Carmichael, 2004; Carroll et al., 1987; Clark & Kenneth, 2012). In the U.S. other social identities increasingly align with partisanship (Mason & Wronski, 2018) and increasingly people also perceive partisanship and ideology as interchangeable concepts (Abramowitz & Saunders, 2006). On the basis of this literature we expect to find partisan differences in punitiveness, leading to

our first hypothesis:

Partisanship Hypothesis (H1): Republicans will express a stronger desire to punish politicians involved in moral transgressions than will Democrats.

People's social identities affect how they interact with in- and out-group members (Gromet & Darley, 2009) since they wish to perceive of themselves and the social group(s) they belong to as moral (Van der Toorn, Ellemers & Doosje, 2015). The group's moral image is even more important than its competence or sociability image (Leach, Ellemers & Barretto, 2007). Consequently, people are typically less tolerant of an immoral in-group member than an incompetent one (Van der Lee et al, 2017). An in-group member committing a moral transgression is a potential threat to the positive moral group image (Van der Lee et al, 2017) and a threat to positive group image is considered a threat to a member's own social identity (Huddy & Bankert, 2017). To create and uphold a positive social identity, people engage in defence mechanisms such as biased information processing, intergroup bias in perceptions, in-group favoritism, and outgroup derogation of behaviours (Huddy & Bankert, 2017). Consequently, people should have a weaker desire to punish transgressors with whom they share identity (Hoffman et al. 2018). However, there is also some research showing a greater willingness to punish in-group transgressors (Vidmar, 2002). Even so, the preponderance of prior research suggests the following hypothesis:

In party Bias Hypothesis (H2): Voters will show a stronger desire to punish out-party politicians involved in moral transgressions than for in-party politicians.

An important predictor of punitiveness is the *perceived severity* of the offense, i.e. people's judgment of moral wrongfulness (Gromet & Darley, 2009). People differ in their

judgment of severity of the same crime (Heffner & Feldman Hall, 2019). The more wrong people consider a moral transgression, the stronger people's intuitive desire to punish the transgressor (Hoffman et al., 2018; Koster, Goudriaan & Van der Schans, 2009; Gromet & Darley, 2009). People want punishment to fit the severity of the offense (Gromet & Darley, 2009). Moreover, the more severe the transgression the more people prefer retributive justice over restorative justice (Gromet & Darley, 2009). Consequently, we formulate our third hypothesis:

Perceived Severity Hypothesis (H3): The more morally wrong voters perceive a politician's moral transgression, the stronger their desire for punishment of the transgressing politician.

Study Design, Stimuli, Data Collection, and Method of Analysis

To examine differences in U.S. partisan voters' desires to punish when confronted with politicians' moral transgressions we conducted a vignette study that incorporated a between-subjects experiment in a 6 x 3 design as part of an online survey. Each respondent was randomly assigned a short vignette describing a fictional, but realistic sounding, scenario in which a politician – randomly assigned to be a Republican, Democrat, or no party – committed a transgression. Respondents viewed a single vignette, eliminating the possibility of spill over effects from viewing multiple types of moral violations. As we aimed to create vignettes encompassing a range of moral principles, we drew inspiration from the Moral Foundation Theory (MFT) framework that distinguishes five moral principles, namely Care, Fairness, Loyalty, Authority and Sanctity (Graham et al. 2011).¹ We added a social norm

¹ We are aware that MFT is contested, namely in the number of moral foundations (e.g. Iurino and Saucier 2020) and the extent to which the so-called "foundations" are causal first principles (Hatemi, Crabtree, & Smith 2019; Ciuk 2018; Smith et al. 2017). We make use of

violation to the moral violations as a potential baseline to make six violation conditions. We analyse the results by combining all five of the moral foundations.² This ensures that results are not limited to a particular type of moral transgression, but robust across a spectrum of moral violations, and the partisan manipulation enables us to test whether voters differ in their desire to punish in-or out-group transgressors.

The six vignettes are displayed in Table 1. We selected these from a pre-test of 30 vignettes using a sample of 555 U. S. respondents recruited through Amazon Mechanical Turk. Vignettes were developed by building on Clifford, et al.’s (2015) standardized vignettes which we slightly modified to fit a political context. Those selected best represent each moral principle and social norm while also being perceived as violating that specific moral principle or social norm, and understandable and realistic. Full details of the study treatment and the pre-test of the 30 possible vignettes are included in the Supplementary Materials.³

Table 1: Six Transgression Vignettes

Violation	Moral Principle	Vignette
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MFT categories simply to provide a broad range of moral transgressions for testing our hypotheses. Scandals come from different actions by politicians, and there are a wide range of moral principles which may be violated.

² Our data set only contains one vignette for each moral principle. Consequently, we are unable to separate the specific effect of that particular moral transgression on voters’ punitiveness from the generic effect of violating that specific moral principle. Therefore, we refrain from assessing the effect of specific moral principles on punitiveness. Future work should include more than a single vignette for each foundation.

³ An anonymous reviewer pointed us to Redlawsk and McCann’s (2005) useful conception of lawbreaking vs. favouritism in corruption, suggesting we might make use of it here. However, we purposely chose vignettes that are clearly morally wrong according to the pre-test, but not necessarily illegal. We do not specify the age of the “teenager” in the Sanctity vignette, which means it is not clearly an illegal act, even if repugnant. Thus, we cannot speak to the distinction between moral violations that break the law and those that are not illegal.

Moral	Care	You see a (Democrat/Republican/-) politician make fun of a constituent with mental health problems
Moral	Fairness	You see a (Democrat/Republican/-) politician making sure that those who voted for him get first access to jobs
Moral	Loyalty	You see a (Democrat/Republican/-) politician town say the neighbouring town is better
Moral	Authority	You see a (Democrat/Republican/-) politician violating safety regulations ordered by the Chief of Police/Chief Constable at a disaster
Moral	Sanctity	You see a (Democrat/Republican/-) politician was found having sex with a teenager
Social Norm	None	You see a (Democrat/Republican/-) politician carrying briefing papers to the capitol/Houses of Parliament in a plastic grocery bag

Note: “-” is a vignette without any partisan label.

Following the pre-test, the main study was conducted between October 2, 2020 and November 3, 2020. We chose the last month of the U.S. Presidential election period to take advantage of voters likely to be especially politically focused, since our underlying interest is understanding precursors to heterogeneous electoral outcomes of moral transgressions. We used Qualtrics to administer the survey online to 2,977 respondents living in the United States, recruited through Dynata (formerly known as Survey Sampling International). The sample is representative of the American adult population on age, gender, race/ethnicity, income, and region of residence, with details displayed in Table A2.2 of the Supplementary Materials. The pre-test and the main study were approved by the institutional review board of [REDACTED for review].

After exposure to the vignette we asked respondents: “When you think about this politician’s behavior, to what extent do you agree with the following statements?” and provided a set of six statements describing theoretical scenarios of both restorative and retributive justice. Respondents were asked to express agreement on a 5-point scale running

Table 2: Punitiveness Scale for Partisans

		Individual Items					
I	Labels	RC	Mean	Std Dev	H _i	Z	DM
1	The politician should apologize	N	3.711	1.433	.761	80.920	Y

	to the public for his/her behavior						
2	The politician should apologize to all parties involved for his/her behavior	N	3.683	1.441	.758	80.832	Y
3	The politician should restore the damage done by his/her behavior	N	3.582	1.393	.718	76.539	Y
4	The politician should be removed from office because of his/her behavior	N	3.097	1.556	.686	72.423	Y
5	The politician should receive a warning for his/her behavior from the party leader	N	3.382	1.486	.650	69.246	Y
6	This politician should because of his/her behavior be reported to authorities	N	3.216	1.563	.701	74.655	Y
Scale							
	Punitiveness, i.e. the desire to punish		Mean	Standard Deviation	H	Z	Rho
			20.670	7.602	.712	131.021	.927

N=2474. Method=Mokken Scale Analysis. Abbreviations: I=Item. RC=Reverse Coded. DM=Double Monotonous. Y=Yes, N=No. Items 1 to 3 were designed as restorative justice items and items 4 to 6 were designed as retributive justice item.

from 1=Not at all to 5=Extremely. Table 2 displays the wording and Mokken scale analysis (Mokken, 2011) for partisans, showing that the six ordinal items constitute a strong uni-dimensional scale with a Homogeneity coefficient of .71⁴ Mokken scaling is a scaling procedure for dichotomous and polytomus items, a homogeneity coefficient of 5 or higher indicates a strong scale (Mokken, 2011).

⁴ The scale included items intending to represent both restorative and retributive justice measures. Research on legal norm transgressions distinguishes between these two. The first aims to correct the harm done to the parties' involved in the transgression and the latter solely to punish the offender involved in the violations for causing harm (Gromet & Darley, 2009). People's default orientation is retributive justice (Gromet and Darley 2009), although measures of restorative and retributive justice are found to be highly intercorrelated (Hoffman et al. 2018). Our descriptive results show that people slightly prefer restorative corrections over retributive corrections, although the Mokken scaling analysis shows the items we chose capture only one concept, namely general punitiveness.

The items measure punitiveness, respondents' desire to punish. Similar results are found when we conduct subgroup Mokken scale analysis for the separate vignettes.⁵ The composite additive scale runs from 6 to 30.⁶

We conduct OLS regressions that include 2,474 observations when examining partisan responses to all vignettes, and 2,074 observations when analyzing partisan responses to moral vignettes only, dropping respondents who viewed the social norm vignette. All models include demographic controls for sex, age, education, race, religious denomination and religiosity. See the Supplementary Materials for full models including the controls.

Initial analyses show that punitive responses to politicians' moral violations significantly differ from responses to violations of a social norm. Respondents exposed to a moral violation score on average 7.5 points higher on the punitiveness scale than respondents exposed to the social norm violation. Sensitivity analyses show that these results are not dependent on specific moral vignettes, as displayed in Table A1.9 of the Supplementary Materials. As our focus here is on moral transgressions, we generally drop all social norm vignette cases for remaining analyses.

Operationalization of Independent and Control Variables

⁵ Additional analyses were conducted and are reported in the Supplementary Materials. The results for the Punitiveness scale reported in Table 2 hold whether or not nonpartisans are included (Table A.1.1). We also provide histograms of distribution of the Punitiveness variable with and without nonpartisans and with and without the social norm vignette in Figures A1.1 to A1.4. Subgroup Mokken scale analyses for the individual vignettes are reported in Tables A1.2 to A1.7.

⁶ The correlation between the Punitiveness Scale and the variable Propensity to Vote, which is measure on a 0-10-point scale (1=Not at all likely;10=Extremely likely) is $-.452$, which indicates a moderate negative relationship between voters' desire to punish and likelihood that they will vote for that politician. The correlation between Perceived Likeability of the Politician (1=Unlikeable; 7=Likeable) and the Punitiveness Scale is $.373$, which indicates a moderate negative relationship between punitiveness and perceived likeability of the candidate. See Table A1.8 in the Supplementary Materials. These correlations indicate that although related these variables measure distinct concepts.

Voter Partisanship is measured using the typical 7-point scale, constructed from a series of questions that first ask whether the respondent is a Democrat, Republican, or Independent, and then ask the strength of the party preference. Independents were asked whether they leaned one way or the other. We use dummy variables representing Republicans (1=Yes;0=No) and Democrats (1=Yes;0=No). Nonpartisans (Independents) (1=Yes; 0=No) are excluded from most analyses since our focus is on partisan effects; only Democrat is entered, leaving Republican as the baseline.

Shared Partisanship (1=Yes; 0=No) is constructed on the basis of the variable Partisanship and the randomized partisanship label of the transgressor depicted in the vignette. The value 1 indicates that the respondent shares partisanship with the politician portrayed in the vignette, with 0 indicating that the respondent and politician do not share partisanship.⁷

Moral Transgression Severity is constructed by asking respondents to indicate how morally wrong they consider the behavior of the politician involved to be. Perceived severity was originally measured on a 5-point scale where 1 indicates Not at all and 5 indicates Extremely. For the purpose of conducting subgroup analyses for different levels of perceived severity of the moral transgression, and considering the small number of observations in the response categories “Not at all wrong” and “Not too wrong,” we recoded the variable. We created three dummy variables, Low Perceived Severity (1=Yes; 0=No), Moderate Perceived Severity (1=Yes; 0=No) and High Perceived Severity (1=Yes; 0=No). To construct the

⁷ Note that we code respondents viewing vignettes without a partisan label as not sharing partisanship. Although we run analyses on solely partisan voters we include the vignettes without partisan labels in our analyses to not further decrease sample size, we would lose an additional 673 observations if we exclude these vignettes. All reported effects of partisanship and shared partisanship on punitiveness remain when we exclude these vignettes without partisan labels from our analyses. See Table A1.12 and Figures 1.5 to 1.9 in the Supplementary Materials.

dummy variable Low Perceived Severity we combined the response categories “Not at all wrong” and “Not too wrong”. To create the dummy variable High Perceived Severity we combined the response categories “Very wrong” and “Extremely wrong.” Remaining respondents were coded as Moderate.

The control variable **Female** is a dummy variable (1=Female; 0=Male). The continuous variable **Age** runs between 18 and 98. Three dummy variables measure respondent’s **Education**; No College Degree (1=Yes; 0=No), Bachelors degree (1=Yes; 0=No) and Postgraduate Degree (1=Yes; 0=No). In all models no college degree serves as reference category. **Race** is measured using a set of five dummy variables; White (1=Yes; 0=No), African American (1=Yes; 0=No), Asian (1=Yes; 0=No) Hispanic (1=Yes; 0=No) and Other (1=Yes; 0=No). The reference category in all models is white. We measure whether the respondent reports to belong to a **Religious Denomination** with a dummy variable (1=Yes; 0=No) while **Religiosity** is the reported frequency of religious service attendance apart from social obligations, which has 7 categories running from Never (1) to More than once a week (7).

Results

OLS regression analyses predicting partisan voters’ responses to moral violations are reported in Table 3 which for interpretation purposes does not display the coefficients of the demographic controls⁸

Model 1 in Table 3 examines the effects of partisanship and shared partisanship without controlling for the perceived severity of the moral transgression. We find a

⁸ The only demographic controls that are consistently significant (although they have only a small effect on punitiveness) are Age and African American. We find that older people score on average -.021 less on the punitiveness scale than younger people. We find that African American partisan voters score on average .851 higher on the punitiveness scale than white partisan voters. No other significant effect for race is found.

significant partisan difference in punitiveness. Nevertheless, the effect runs opposite to our hypothesis, with Democrats on average 1.63 points more strongly desiring to punish

Table 3: Effects of Partisanship, Shared Partisanship and Perceived Severity on Voters' Punitiveness to Transgressing Politicians

	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4	Model 5
Democrat	1.626** (.333)	1.617** (.332)	1.202** (.398)	.510 ^o (.304)	-2.939** (.836)
Shared Partisanship		-1.126** (.324)	-1.799** (.482)	-.596 ^o (.368)	-2.253** (.850)
Democrat* Shared Partisanship			1.231 (.652)	.224 (.497)	1.802 (1.321)
Moderate Severity				4.235** (.412)	1.879** (.716)
High Severity				11.956** (.356)	9.857** (.601)
Democrat* Moderate Severity					4.132** (1.040)
Democrat* High Severity					3.837** (.893)
Shared Partisanship * Moderate Severity					1.223** (1.130)
Shared Partisanship * High Severity					2.295* (.977)
Democrat * Shared Partisanship * Moderate Severity					.365 (1.701)
Democrat * Shared Partisanship * High Severity					-2.516 ^o (1.460)
Constant	19.530** (.598)	19.952** (.609)	20.223** (.625)	13.280** (.541)	15.170** (.679)
r ²	.024	.030	.032	.440	.449
N	2076	2076	2076	2076	2076

*Note: OLS regression. Standard errors are displayed in parentheses. *p<.05, **p<.01. The reference group for the variable severity is low severity, which combines the original response categories 'Not at all wrong' and 'Not too wrong'. The effects of the demographic control variables are not displayed. See Table 1.10 in the Supplementary Materials for the full models.*

politicians' immoral behaviour than Republicans. Turning to Model 2, when we add shared partisanship to the model, we also find an in-party bias for punitiveness. Partisans on average are about 1.13 points less desiring of punishing in-party politicians than out-party politicians.

Differences by party are examined in Model 3, which finds that the in-party bias is asymmetric. Republicans significantly differ in punitive response when exposed to in-party versus out-party transgressors, at nearly 1.8 points lower in their desire to punish in-party politicians (baseline shared partisanship coefficient). Democrats do not significantly differ in punitiveness whether the moral transgressor is an in- or out-party politician as shown by the non-significant interaction between partisanship and shared partisanship. In sum, across these three models, we find that our first hypothesis is not supported, as it is Democrats who are overall more desiring of punishment than Republicans. Our second hypothesis, which suggested an in-party bias, is partially supported in that we see such bias only for Republican voters and not for Democrats.

Our third hypothesis tests the extent to which the perceived severity of the moral transgression conditions punitiveness responses. Model 4 reports this analysis. Voters' perceived severity of the moral transgression has a very large effect upon their desire for punishment, supporting H3. As perceived severity increases, so does the wish to punish the transgressor. Voters who perceive the moral transgression they viewed as highly severe are on average 11.96 points higher on punitiveness than voters perceiving the moral transgression as low in severity. Figure 1 provides a visual representation of the effect.

After finding (partial) support for our hypotheses, with the exception of the Partisanship Hypothesis (H1), we examine whether the effects remain while controlling for perceived severity of the moral transgressions. When we control for voters' perception of the severity of the moral transgression they viewed, the effect of partisanship becomes smaller, as Democrats score only .58 higher on punitiveness than Republicans in response to politicians' immoral behaviour. Estimating the significance of the contrast, we find it remains statistically significant ($F=.583, p=.022$). However, Figure 3 shows that after controlling for perceived severity of the moral transgression, the significance of the in-party bias for

Republicans (Model 3) disappears ($F=2.63, p=.105$).

Figure 1: The Effect of Perceived Severity of the Moral Transgression on Voters' Punitiveness in Response to Politicians' Moral Transgressions

Note: N=2076. The figure is based on marginal effects with 95% confidence intervals estimated after OLS regression Model 4 in Table 3.

Yet, the results are more complex than they appear in Figures 2 and 3. Although we did not develop an *a priori* hypothesis covering the complexity we find here, examining three-way interactions between voter partisanship, shared partisanship, and severity (Model 5 in Table 3) finds that the effects of partisanship and shared partisanship differ across perceived levels of severity, as displayed in Figures 4 and 5, derived from Model 5. Starting with partisan heterogeneity generally, we find that when voters perceive the severity of the moral transgression to be low, Democrats have on average a 2.23-point weaker desire to punish than Republicans ($F=11.61, p=.000$). When voters perceive the severity of the moral transgression to be moderate, the direction of the effect reverses, with Democrats on average 1.95-points stronger in their desire to punish than Republicans ($F= 13.92, p=.000$). At the

highest level of severity, the effect attenuates, with Democrats showing only a 0.681-point

Figure 2: The Effect of Partisanship on Voters' Punitiveness in Response to Politicians' Moral Transgressions

Note: N=2076. The figure is based on marginal effects with 95% confidence intervals estimated after OLS regression Model 1 and OLS regression Model 3 in Table 3.

Figure 3: The In-party Bias of Voters' Punitiveness in Response to Politicians' Moral Transgressions

Note: $N=2076$. The figure is based on marginal effects with 95 % confidence intervals estimated after OLS regression Model 3 and OLS regression Model 4 in Table 3.

stronger desire to punish than Republicans ($F=5.11, p=.023$). These effects are displayed in Figure 4.

Figure 4 The Effect of Partisanship on Voters' Punitiveness of Politicians' Moral Transgressions at Different Levels of Perceived Severity

Note: N=2076. The figure is based on marginal effects with 95% confidence intervals estimated after OLS regression Model 5 in Table 3.

These unanticipated findings show the importance of examining different levels of perceived severity of moral violations by politicians. This leads us to also examine in-party bias by levels of severity, as displayed in Figure 5. Ultimately, by examining severity, we find just partial support for our In-Party Bias Hypothesis (H2). When examining the effect of shared partisanship at different perceived levels of severity, we only see a significant in-party bias for Republicans at the lowest level of severity. When Republican voters perceive the severity of the moral transgression to be low, they have on average a 2.25-point stronger desire to punish the out-party transgressor than the in-party transgressor ($F= 7.03, p=.008$). However, this Republican voters in-party bias disappears at higher levels of perceived severity. Democrats do not show an in-party bias at any level of severity. We therefore find only conditional support for the In Party Bias Hypothesis (H2).

Figure 5 In-party Bias of Democrats and Republicans' Punitiveness of Politicians' Moral Transgressions at Different Levels of Severity

Note: N=2076. The figure is based on marginal effects with 95% confidence intervals estimated after OLS regression Model 5, in Table 3

Our findings that the effects of partisanship and especially shared partisanship on voters’ punitiveness are substantially reduced when controlling for perceived severity suggest that the partisanship/shared partisanship effects on punitiveness are strongly mediated by perceived severity of the moral transgression. Partisanship and shared partisanship have more of an indirect than direct effect on punitiveness. Republicans and Democrats differ in how severe they perceive politicians’ moral transgressions which then leads to the effects we find.

Conclusion

This study argues that to understand voters’ heterogeneous electoral responses to moral transgressions, we should look at punitiveness, i.e. voters intuitive desire for moral punishment. We view punitiveness as a precursor to holding politicians’ electorally

accountable and find that levels of punitiveness when faced with moral violations strongly differ on the basis of severity, partisanship and shared partisanship. When voters perceive the severity of a moral violation to be low, Republicans have a greater desire to punish than Democrats, and Republicans' levels of punitiveness depend on the group of the transgressor, with more desire to punish the out-party than the in-party transgressor. When voters perceive the severity of the moral transgression to be moderate or high, Democrats have a stronger desire to punish the politician involved than Republicans. But regardless of the perceived severity of the moral transgression, Democrats do not show an in-party bias in their desire to punish. Not only do the results show partisan voters' heterogeneity in punitiveness, but also that this relationship is strongly mediated by perceived severity. Our study thus shows the value of the concept of punitiveness for the study of political scandals.

A limitation of this study is that it took place during a highly contested U.S. Presidential election with a Republican incumbent known for continual moral violations. At some point it will be important to understand how the effects we find are conditioned on Donald Trump's leadership of the Republican Party, especially given the unexpected finding that Republican voters in our study are lower in their desire for punishment. This will, of course, have to wait until Trump is off the public stage. Other recent research supports these unexpected partisan differences (Morais, Abrams & Randsley de Moura, 2020; Howard, Cervone & Motyl, 2022). Republicans are more likely to vote for the in-group candidate than Democrats when the candidate is involved in a severe moral transgression, which Howard, Cervone & Motyl, (2022) suggest signals greater in-group loyalty. Morais, Abrams & Randsley de Moura (2020) also find that the Trump era affects how Republicans, in particular Trump supporters, look at morally transgressive behavior. They report that Hillary Clinton supporters were less acceptable of unethical leadership than Trump supporters even prior to 2016. After the 2016 presidential election the partisan gap became larger as Clinton

supporters even became less acceptable of unethical leadership and Trump supporters became more tolerant .

In addition, future work should examine voters' severity perceptions of moral transgressions as our findings suggest that voters' perceptions of perceived severity strongly mediate the relationship between partisanship and shared partisanship with punitiveness. Some of our findings suggest also partisan differences in how severe voters perceive politicians' moral transgressions, in particular that Republicans are less likely to consider moral transgressions to be highly severe. Finally, scholars could extend this research using voters' levels of punitiveness to predict electoral support for moral transgressors. We were also limited in our ability to examine specific types of moral violations, including particular moral principles or the issue of illegality (Redlawsk and McCann 2005). Future research should attempt to disentangle the questions of whether violations of specific moral principles are more or less likely to result in desire for punishment. Our results provide additional understanding of why there is heterogeneity in voter responses to scandals, with many politicians surviving scandalous behaviour when it comes time for election. One factor is likely to be voters' desire for punishment, which appears to be conditioned on partisanship and perceptions of the severity of the moral violation. Given that lower perceived severity correlates with lower desire for punishment, investigating what makes a violation more or less severe in voters eyes would be a reasonable next step.

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Appendix 1 Full Models

Table A1.1: Punitiveness Scale All Respondents All Vignettes

Individual Items							
I	Labels	RC	Mean	SD	H _i	Z	DM
1	The politician should apologize to the public for his/her behavior	N	3.659	1.454	.766	89.403	Y
2	The politician should apologize to all parties involved for his/her behavior	N	3.633	1.464	.764	89.392	Y
3	The politician should restore the damage done by his/her behavior	N	3.527	1.421	.716	83.924	Y
4	The politician should be removed from office because of his/her behavior	N	3.053	1.555	.691	80.078	Y
5	The politician should receive a warning for his/her behavior from the party leader	N	3.329	1.496	.655	76.537	Y
6	This politician should because of his/her behavior be reported to authorities	N	3.165	1.571	.716	82.645	Y
Scale							
	Punitiveness, i.e. the desire to punish		Mean	SD	H	Z	Rho
			20.366	7.698	.7159	144.735	.933

N=2977. Method=Mokken Scale Analysis. Abbreviations: I=Item. RC=Reverse Coded. SD=Standard Deviation. DM=Double Monotonous. Y=Yes, N=No. Items 1 to 3 were designed as restorative justice items and items 4 to 6 were designed as retributive justice items.

Table A1.2: Punitiveness Scale All Respondents Exposed to a Care Violation

Individual Items						
I	Labels	RC	Mean	H _i	Z	DM
1	The politician should apologize to the public for his/her behavior	N	4.033	.736	33.293	Y
2	The politician should apologize to all parties involved for his/her behavior	N	4.073	.711	32.021	Y
3	The politician should restore the damage done by his/her behavior	N	3.870	.700	32.425	Y
4	The politician should be removed from office because of his/her behavior	N	3.136	.611	27.653	Y
5	The politician should receive a warning for his/her behavior from the party leader	N	3.690	.640	29.719	Y
6	This politician should because of his/her behavior be reported to authorities	N	3.073	.605	27.156	Y

Scale						
				H	Z	Rho
				.664	52.212	.921

N=493. Method=Mokken Scale Analysis. Abbreviations: I=Item. RC=Reverse Coded. DM=Double Monotonous. Y=Yes, N=No. Items 1 to 3 were designed as restorative justice items and items 4 to 6 were designed as retributive justice items.

Table A1.3: Punitiveness Scale All Respondents Exposed to a Fairness Violation

Individual Items						
I	Labels	RC	Mean	H _i	Z	DM
1	The politician should apologize to the public for his/her behavior	N	3.908	.743	35.048	Y
2	The politician should apologize to all parties involved for his/her behavior	N	3.871	.768	36.336	Y
3	The politician should restore the damage done by his/her behavior	N	3.806	.724	34.292	Y
4	The politician should be removed from office because of his/her behavior	N	3.533	.684	32.259	Y
5	The politician should receive a warning for his/her behavior from the party leader	N	3.700	.646	30.657	Y
6	This politician should because of his/her behavior be reported to authorities	N	3.531	.708	33.442	Y
Scale						
				H	Z	Rho
						.931

N=490. Method=Mokken Scale Analysis. Abbreviations: I=Item. RC=Reverse Coded. DM=Double Monotonous. Y=Yes, N=No. Items 1 to 3 were designed as restorative justice items and items 4 to 6 were designed as retributive justice items.

Table A1.4: Punitiveness Scale All Respondents Exposed to a Loyalty Violation

Individual Items						
I	Labels	RC	Mean	H _i	Z	DM
1	The politician should apologize to the public for his/her behavior	N	3.251	.7241	33.665	Y
2	The politician should apologize to all parties involved for his/her behavior	N	3.131	.719	33.942	Y
3	The politician should restore the damage done by his/her behavior	N	3.113	.657	30.931	Y
4	The politician should be removed from office because of his/her behavior	N	2.376	.657	30.429	Y

5	The politician should receive a warning for his/her behavior from the party leader	N	2.787	.687	32.409	Y
6	This politician should because of his/her behavior be reported to authorities	N	2.318	.637	29.156	Y
Scale						
				H	Z	Rho
				.681	55.018	.923

N=503. Method=Mokken Scale Analysis. Abbreviations: I=Item. RC=Reverse Coded. DM=Double Monotonous. Y=Yes, N=No. Items 1 to 3 were designed as restorative justice items and items 4 to 6 were designed as retributive justice items.

Table A1.5: Punitiveness Scale All Respondents Exposed to an Authority Violation

Individual Items						
I	Labels	RC	Mean	H _i	Z	DM
1	The politician should apologize to the public for his/her behavior	N	3.8919	.68291	31.5524	Y
2	The politician should apologize to all parties involved for his/her behavior	N	3.9252	.70250	32.1953	Y
3	The politician should restore the damage done by his/her behavior	N	3.7963	.65095	30.3713	Y
4	The politician should be removed from office because of his/her behavior	N	3.0187	.56048	25.1471	Y
5	The politician should receive a warning for his/her behavior from the party leader	N	3.6944	.60315	28.0744	Y
6	This politician should because of his/her behavior be reported to authorities	N	3.5135	.67147	30.7449	Y
Scale						
				H	Z	Rho
				.644	51.238	.910

N=481. Method=Mokken Scale Analysis. Abbreviations: I=Item. RC=Reverse Coded. DM=Double Monotonous. Y=Yes, N=No. Items 1 to 3 were designed as restorative justice items and items 4 to 6 were designed as retributive justice items.

Table A1.6: Punitiveness Scale All Respondents Exposed to a Sanctity Violation

Individual Items						
I	Labels	RC	Mean	H _i	Z	DM
1	The politician should apologize to the public for his/her behavior	N	3.734	.807	38.912	Y

2	The politician should apologize to all parties involved for his/her behavior	N	3.702	.800	38.665	Y
3	The politician should restore the damage done by his/her behavior	N	3.604	.722	34.642	Y
4	The politician should be removed from office because of his/her behavior	N	3.425	.750	36.089	Y
5	The politician should receive a warning for his/her behavior from the party leader	N	3.306	.602	28.817	Y
6	This politician should because of his/her behavior be reported to authorities	N	3.624	.780	37.682	Y
Scale						
				H	Z	Rho
				.743	61.946	.940

N=497. Method=Mokken Scale Analysis. Abbreviations: I=Item. RC=Reverse Coded. DM=Double Monotonous. Y=Yes, N=No. Items 1 to 3 were designed as restorative justice items and items 4 to 6 were designed as retributive justice items.

Table A1.7: Punitiveness Scale All Respondents Exposed to a Social Norm Violation

Individual Items						
I	Labels	RC	Mean	H _i	Z	DM
1	The politician should apologize to the public for his/her behavior	N	2.470	.821	39.710	Y
2	The politician should apologize to all parties involved for his/her behavior	N	2.390	.793	38.296	Y
3	The politician should restore the damage done by his/her behavior	N	2.478	.777	37.453	Y
4	The politician should be removed from office because of his/her behavior	N	2.0260	.770	36.126	Y
5	The politician should receive a warning for his/her behavior from the party leader	N	2.484	.780	37.588	Y
6	This politician should because of his/her behavior be reported to authorities	N	2.144	.780	37.074	Y
Scale						
				H	Z	Rho
				.787	65.333	.952

N=500. Method=Mokken Scale Analysis. Abbreviations: I=Item. RC=Reverse Coded. DM=Double Monotonous. Y=Yes, N=No. Items 1 to 3 were designed as restorative justice items and items 4 to 6 were designed as retributive justice items.

Figure A1.1 Distribution Dependent Variable Punitiveness All Respondents Exposed to Transgressions

Figure A1.2 Distribution Dependent Variable Punitiveness Respondents Exposed to Moral Transgressions

Figure A1.3 Distribution Dependent Variable Punitiveness Partisan Respondents Exposed to Transgressions

Figure A1.4 Distribution Dependent Variable Punitiveness Partisan Respondents Exposed to Moral Transgressions

Table A1.8 Correlations between Punitiveness, Propensity to Vote and Perceived Candidate Traits

	Including Nonpartisans	Excluding Nonpartisans
Perceived moral character politician	-.498	-.491
Perceived competence politician	-.464	-.456
Perceived trustworthiness politician	-.493	-.484
Perceived likeability politician	-.463	-.452
Propensity to vote for politician	-.384	-.373
N	2967	2464

Table A1.9 Sensitivity Analyses of the Effect of Moral Violations on Partisan Voters' Punitiveness to Transgressing Politicians

	All Vignettes	Without Care	Without Fairness	Without Loyalty	Without Authority	Without Sanctity
Moral Violation	7.499** (.387)	7.502** (.397)	7.326** (.399)	8.627** (.371)	7.454** (.404)	6.578** (.398)
Female	.606* (.209)	.391 (.332)	.631 ^o (.330)	.547 ^o (.309)	.616 ^o (.336)	.396 (.332)
Age	.006 (.009)	.002 (.010)	.002 (.010)	.014 (.009)	.004 (.010)	-.008 (.010)
Bachelor degree	-.156 (.331)	.264 (.365)	-.079 (.366)	.052 (.340)	-.426 (.372)	-.509 (.368)
Postgraduate Degree	-.184 (.394)	-.268 (.434)	-.189 (.436)	-.354 (.412)	-.104 (.439)	-.196 (.437)
African American	1.696** (.439)	1.853** (.490)	2.032** (.485)	1.207** (.449)	1.395** (.490)	2.193** (.489)
Asian	.084 (.681)	.236 (.752)	.197 (.771)	.238 (.712)	.113 (.762)	-.016 (.742)
Hispanic	.032 (.514)	-.260 (.573)	.135 (.577)	-.272 (.529)	.564 (.577)	.199 (.564)
Other	-.410 (.783)	-.146 (.860)	-.866 (.902)	.140 (.830)	-.458 (.840)	-.751 (.870)
No Religious Denomination	-.134 (.374)	-.390 (.414)	-.292 (.416)	-.105 (.386)	-.0418 (.418)	-.094 (.415)
Religiosity	.054 (.091)	.061 (.101)	.056 (.101)	.041 (.094)	.147 (.103)	-.006 (.102)
Constant	13.606** (.633)	13.995** (.679)	13.694** (.681)	13.426** (.634)	13.434** (.696)	14.398** (.686)
R square	.140	.158	.152	.213	.149	.130
N	2474	2051	2068	2061	2067	2047

*Note: Model run is OLS regression. Standard errors are displayed in parentheses. ^ois significant at level 0.10 * is significant at level 0.05 ** is significant at level 0.01. Regression analyses are restricted to partisans. Column 3-7 present the results of sensitivity analyses using a jack-knife procedure in which we drop one vignette at the time.*

Table A1.10 The Effect of Partisanship, Shared Partisanship and Perceived Severity on Voters' Punitiveness to Transgressing Politicians (Full Models)

	Model 1	Model2	Model 3	Model 4	Model 5
Democrat	1.626** (.333)	1.617** (.332)	1.202** (.398)	.510 ^o (.304)	-2.939** (.836)
Shared Partisanship		-1.126** (.324)	-1.799** (.482)	-.596 ^o (.368)	-2.253** (.850)
Democrat* Shared Partisanship			1.231 ^o (.652)	.224 (.497)	1.802 (1.321)
Moderate Severity				4.235** (.412)	1.879** (.716)
High Severity				11.956** (.356)	9.857** (.601)
Democrat* Moderate Severity					4.132** (1.040)
Democrat* High Severity					3.837** (.893)
Shared Partisanship * Moderate Severity					1.223** (1.130)
Shared Partisanship * High Severity					2.295* (.977)
Democrat * Shared Partisanship * Moderate Severity					.365 (1.701)
Democrat *Shared Partisanship * High Severity					-2.516 ^o (1.460)
Female	.951** (.321)	.952** (.320)	.948** (.320)	.044 (.244)	.021 (.242)
Age	.020* (.009)	.019* (.009)	.019* (.009)	.020* (.007)	.021* (.007)
Bachelor degree	.225 (.355)	.236 (.354)	.228 (.353)	.172 (.269)	.176 (.267)
Postgraduate Degree	-.011 (.422)	-.021 (.421)	-.027 (.421)	.477 (.321)	.501 (.319)
African American	.767 (.494)	.805 (.493)	.840 ^o (.492)	.796* (.375)	.851* (.372)
Asian	-.552 (.723)	-.592 (.721)	-.599 (.721)	-.310 (.549)	-.280 (.546)
Hispanic	-.685 (.560)	-.701 (.558)	-.704 (.558)	-.461 (.425)	-.527 (.422)
Other	-.602 (.832)	-.624 (.829)	-.605 (.829)	.137 (.632)	.119 (.629)
No Religious Denomination	-.134 (.404)	-.166 (.403)	-.161 (.403)	-.139 (.307)	-.078 (.305)
Religiosity	.085 (.099)	.077 (.099)	.065 (.099)	.044 (.075)	.034 (.075)
Constant	19.530** (.598)	19.952** (.609)	20.223** (.625)	13.280** (.541)	15.170** (.679)
R square	.024	.030	.032	.440	.449

N	2076	2076	2076	2076	2076
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Note: Model run is OLS regression. Standard errors are displayed in parentheses. ^ois significant at level 0.10 * is significant at level 0.05 ** is significant at level 0.01 The reference group for the variable severity is low severity, which combines the original response categories 'Not at all wrong' and 'Not too wrong'. See for more details on the demographic control the operationalization section in the main manuscript. For the variable race the reference category is white.

Table A1.11 Number of Observations in Cells

Shared Partisanship by Party			
	<i>Out party</i>	<i>In party</i>	
Republicans	632	308	940
Democrats	769	367	1136
	1401	675	2076
Shared Partisanship by Party Per Level of Perceived Severity			
Low Perceived Severity Level			
	<i>Out party</i>	<i>In party</i>	
Republicans	93	64	157
Democrats	71	43	114
	164	107	271
Moderate Perceived Severity Level			
	<i>Out party</i>	<i>In party</i>	
Republicans	125	81	206
Democrats	147	65	212
	272	146	418
High Perceived Severity Level			
	<i>Out party</i>	<i>In party</i>	
Republicans	414	163	577
Democrats	551	259	810
	965	422	1387

Table A1.12 The Effect of Partisanship, Shared Partisanship and Perceived Severity on Voters' Punitiveness to Transgressing Politicians Without Nonpartisan Vignettes (Sensitivity Analyses)

	Model 1	Model2	Model 3	Model 4	Model 5
Democrat	1.450** (.402)	1.431** (.400)	.507 (.541)	.383 (.418)	-3.174** (1.214)
Shared Partisanship		-1.655** (.367)	-2.683** (.547)	-.924* (.426)	-3.996** (1.057)
Democrat* Shared Partisanship			1.868** (.739)	.377 (.572)	2.006 (1.584)
Moderate Severity				3.800** (.507)	-.157 (1.108)
High Severity				11.529** (.436)	3.882** (1.287)
Democrat* Moderate Severity					3.256** (1.411)

Democrat* High Severity					3.814** (1.184)
Shared Partisanship * Moderate Severity					1.223** (1.130)
Shared Partisanship * High Severity					2.295* (.977)
Democrat * Shared Partisanship * Moderate Severity					-.111 (2.040)
Democrat *Shared Partisanship * High Severity					-2.525 (1.728)
Constant	19.403** (.726)	20.279** (.747)	20.868** (.781)	13.845** (.684)	15.170** (.679)
R square	.024	.038	.043	.430	.443
N	1403	1403	1403	1403	1403

*Note: Model run is OLS regression. Standard errors are displayed in parentheses. ° is significant at level 0.10 * is significant at level 0.05 ** is significant at level 0.01 The reference group for the variable severity is low severity, which combines the original response categories 'Not at all wrong' and 'Not too wrong'. See for more details on the demographic control the operationalization section. The effects of the demographic control variables are not displayed. This is the same table as Table 1 in the main manuscript, but the analyses are only ran using partisan respondents exposed to vignettes with partisan labels, all neutral vignettes are dropped.*

Figure A1.5 The Effect of Perceived Severity of the Moral Transgression on Voters' Punitiveness in Response to Politicians' Moral Transgressions Without Nonpartisan Vignettes

Note: N=1403. The figure is based on marginal effects with 95% confidence intervals estimated after OLS regression Model 4. See for Model 4 Table A1.12. The figure was constructed as part of the sensitivity analyses conducted.

Figure A1.6 The Effect of Partisanship on Voters' Punitiveness in Response to Politicians' Moral Transgressions Without Nonpartisan Vignettes

Note: N=1403. The figure is based on marginal effects with 95% confidence intervals estimated after OLS regression Model 1 and OLS regression Model 3. See for Model 1 and Model 4 Table A1.12. The figure was constructed as part of the sensitivity analyses conducted. The figure was constructed as part of the sensitivity analyses conducted.

Figure A1.7: The In-party Bias of Voters' Punitiveness in Response to Politicians' Moral Transgressions Without Nonpartisan Vignettes

Note: N=1403. Figure is based on marginal effects with 95 % confidence intervals estimated after OLS regression Model 3 and OLS regression Model 4. See for Model 3 and Model 4 Table A1.12. The figure was constructed as part of the sensitivity analyses conducted.

Figure A1.8 The Effect of Partisanship on Voters' Punitiveness of Politicians' Moral Transgressions at Different Levels of Perceived Severity Without Nonpartisan Vignettes

Note: N=1403. Figure is based on marginal effects with 95% confidence intervals estimated after OLS regression Model 5. See for Model 5 Table A1.12. The figure was constructed as part of the sensitivity analyses conducted.

Figure A1.9 In-party Bias of Democrats and Republicans' Punitiveness of Politicians' Moral Transgressions at Different Levels of Severity Without Nonpartisan Vignettes

Note: N=1403. Figure is based on marginal effects with 95% confidence intervals estimated after OLS regression Model 5. See for Model 5 Table A1.12. The figure was constructed as part of the sensitivity analyses conducted.

Appendix 2 Study Details

Table A2.1: Treatment Groups Vignette Study

	Moral Foundation Violated	Partisanship Actor
1	Care	Republican
2	Care	Democrat
3	Care	Non-partisan
4	Fairness	Republican
5	Fairness	Democrat
6	Fairness	Non-partisan
7	Loyalty	Republican
8	Loyalty	Democrat
9	Loyalty	Non-partisan
10	Authority	Republican
11	Authority	Democrat
12	Authority	Non-partisan
13	Sanctity	Republican
14	Sanctity	Democrat
15	Sanctity	Non-partisan
16	Social Norm	Republican
17	Social Norm	Democrat
18	Social Norm	Non-partisan

Table A2.2: Sample Demographics

Variable	
% Female	52.65
Mean Age (standard deviation)	33.53 (.30)
% White	69.75
% African American	12.42
% Hispanic	8.81
% Asian	5.16
% Native American	.76
% No college degree	49.48
% Bachelor degree	31.54
% Postgraduate degree	18.98
% Democrat	45.27
% Republican	37.85
% Nonpartisan	16.87
% Conservative	32.98
% Moderate	40.96
% Liberal	26.06
% No religion/ Spiritual/ Atheist/ Agnost	27.30
% Christian	63.58
% Jewish	4.14
% Born Again Christian If Christian	57.60
% Attending Religious Services Once a Month or More	32.64

N=2993. For the Variable Born Again Christian N=1967

Table A2.3: Randomization Checks

Variable	Chi Square (p.value) at 17 degrees of freedom
Female (0-1)	4.67 (.099)
Age (Anova)	.57 (.916)
White (0-1)	21.359 (.221)
African American (0-1)	16.957 (.457)
Hispanic (0-1)	16.124 (.515)
Asian (0-1)	10.453(.884)
Native (0-1)	17.014 (.453)
Education (0-2) (Anova)	.82 (.6715)
Democrat (0-1)	16.297 (.503)
Republican (0-1)	13.419 (.708)
Nonpartisan (0-1)	13.934 (.672)
Political views (0-4)	1.40 (.128)
Denomination (Anova)	1.15 (.302)

Note: To further assess balance, we estimated a multinomial logistic regression model using the variables in the table to predict treatment assignment. The chi-square from this model 312.50 (.652) indicating that the variables do not jointly predict treatment assignment. N=2993.

Appendix 3 Stimulus Material

Vignette 1 Harm/Care, Republican

You see a Republican politician make fun of a constituent with mental health problems.

Vignette 2 Harm/Care, Democrat

You see a Democratic politician make fun of a constituent with mental health problems.

Vignette 3 Harm/Care, Non-partisan

You see a politician make fun of a constituent with mental health problems.

Vignette 4 Fairness/Reciprocity, Republican

You see a Republican politician making sure that those who voted for him get first access to jobs.

Vignette 5 Fairness/Reciprocity, Democrat

You see a Democratic politician making sure that those who voted for him get first access to jobs.

Vignette 6 Fairness/Reciprocity, Non-partisan

You see a politician making sure that those who voted for him get first access to jobs.

Vignette 7 Ingroup/Loyalty, Republican

You see a Republican politician in your town say the neighboring town is better.

Vignette 8 Ingroup/Loyalty, Democrat

You see a Democratic politician in your town say the neighboring town is better.

Vignette 9 Ingroup/Loyalty, Non-partisan

You see a politician in your town say the neighboring town is better.

Vignette 10 Authority/Respect, Republican

You see a Republican politician violating safety regulations ordered by the Chief of Police at a disaster.

Vignette 11 Authority/Respect, Democrat

You see a Democratic politician violating safety regulations ordered by the Chief of Police at a disaster.

Vignette 12 Authority/Respect, Non-partisan

You see a politician violating safety regulations ordered by the Chief of Police at a disaster.

Vignette 13 Purity/Sanctity, Republican

You see a Republican politician was found having sex with a teenager.

Vignette 14 Purity/Sanctity, Democrat

You see a Democratic politician was found having sex with a teenager.

Vignette 15 Purity/Sanctity, Non-partisan

You see a politician was found having sex with a teenager.

Vignette 16 Social Norms, Republican

You see a Republican politician carrying briefing papers to the capitol in a plastic grocery bag

Vignette 17 Social Norms, Democrat

You see a Democratic politician carrying briefing papers to the capitol in a plastic grocery bag

Vignette 18 Social Norms, Non-partisan

You see a politician carrying briefing papers to the capitol in a plastic grocery bag

Appendix 4 Selection of Vignettes and Pre-Tests

In our survey of voters' response to moral transgressions by politicians we randomly presented respondents with a single vignette out of a set of 18 vignettes. The vignettes differ in violation of moral foundation (Care, Fairness, Loyalty, Authority, Sanctity) and whether or not partisan labels were used (None, Democrat, or Republican). In addition, a social norm (i.e., non-moral) violation vignette is included as a control stimulus. The inclusion of the control stimulus allows for a comparison between appraisals of scenarios that depict a moral violation and scenarios that depict a social, but not moral, violation. The vignettes were developed and pre-tested by the authors, selected from a total of 30 vignettes. These 30 vignettes present different scenarios in which a politician violates one of the five different moral foundations or a social norm (i.e., unconventional behaviour and non-moral violation). The vignettes were tested without partisan labels to avoid association with the moral foundation Loyalty. These 30 vignettes were developed on the basis of work by Clifford et al. (2015) and XXX. Clifford et al. (2015) presents a standardized stimulus database of scenarios based on Moral Foundation Theory (MFT) and also uses as control stimulus a social norm violation. We translated some of Clifford et al. (2015) scenarios to the realm of politics, we included the five vignettes used in XXX and developed some additional vignettes. The vignettes contain scenarios that can plausibly occur in everyday politics. We developed scenarios with the realm of US politics in mind.

Like Clifford et al. (2015) we made an effort to eliminate any reference to other foundations to increase the likelihood of isolating the influence of a particular moral foundation. In addition, we stick to Clifford et al. (2015)'s vignette formulation of "You see..." to encourage respondents to visualize themselves as third party witnesses. So in this case all the vignettes start with You see a politician... , see Tables A4.2 for the complete list of vignettes that were pre-tested. The moral foundation Care has three forms of harm, namely emotional harm to a human, physical harm to a human, and physical harm to a non-human animal. We focus solely on emotional harm to a human as the other forms are less likely to occur in everyday politics.

The 30 vignettes were pretested between 16 and 18 June using Amazon's Mechanical Turk (MTurk). We had a sample of 555 MTurk respondents, see Table A4.1 for the sample demographics. Each respondent was presented with a random set of twelve of the vignettes such that each vignettes was approximately rated by 220 respondents to ensure stability of average ratings and enable further psychometric analyses.

After exposure to each vignette the respondents were asked (1) to rate how morally wrong the behavior is on a 5-point scale (labeled not at all wrong, not too wrong, somewhat wrong, very wrong, extremely wrong) and (2) state why the behavior was wrong. The respondents were asked to select one response that best described why they thought the behavior was wrong (it violates moral norms of (a) harm or care; (b) fairness or justice; (c) loyalty; (d) respecting authority; (e) purity or (f) it violates social norms but does not violate a moral norm. Table A4.3 includes the US respondents' ratings for each vignette. After asking these two questions, respondents were asked how understandable the scenario is and how easily they could imagine what happened in the scenario. Both questions provided a 4-point response scale ranging from very easy to very difficult. The last column in the table displays the percentage of respondents that found the scenario very easy or easy to imagine. All scenarios except for the following scored 5 per cent or less on the category very difficult to imagine: 'You see a politician watching videos of people having sex with animals'; ' You see a politician eating tomato soup with a fork at a restaurant'; 'You see a politician celebrate after losing an election' and 'You see a politician wearing a dirty t-shirt and torn jeans at their own

inauguration’. On the basis of these scores, we will not take the item ‘You see a politician watching videos of people having sex with animals’ in consideration for the vignette selection for the survey embedded vignette experiment.

The results show that the vignettes developed to reflect Care and Fairness score the best in terms of correct categorization. The vignettes developed to reflect Sanctity score well in terms of accurate classification, with exception of the vignette ‘You see a married politician is having extramarital homosexual relationships’. Somewhat more challenging is the development of Authority vignettes as the percentage of respondents that correctly classifies the vignettes is considerably lower than for the foundations Care, Fairness and Sanctity. Nevertheless, still people classify the formulated vignettes foremost as Authority. The vignettes that we developed to represent Loyalty and Social Norms perform the weakest as they are not always correctly classified. For instance the vignette ‘You see a politician refusing to sing the national anthem when others are singing it’, was developed as a Loyalty vignette, but is perceived by respondents in both countries as Authority. Overall, we would say that it is very difficult to formulate vignettes that by all respondents are accurately classified, even the best performing vignette is only correctly classified by 87 per cent of the respondents. The Social Norm vignettes are considered by more respondents not at all wrong than the other vignettes. However, the question is if they should as behaviour defying social norms might not be wrong just odd. The pre-test displayed is not our first attempt, we have done a previous pre-test with 25 different vignettes. The Loyalty and Social Norms vignettes also performed moderately in this pre-test.

The six vignettes actually used in our experimental study are selected out of this pool of 30 vignettes on the basis of the following four criteria: 1) highest accurate categorization of the first mode and for the second mode lowest score possible; 2) highest score in terms of perceived moral wrongness; 3) imaginability of the scenario is high. Selection on the basis of these criteria has led to the following set of vignettes, see Table A4.1. We feel most content with the vignettes selected for the foundations Care, Fairness, Authority and Sanctity.

Table A4.1: Selected Vignettes on Basis Pre-Tests

Vignette Care: You see a politician make fun of a constituent with mental health problems								
<i>Care</i>	<i>Fairness</i>	<i>Loyalty</i>	<i>Authority</i>	<i>Sanctity</i>	<i>Social Norms</i>	<i>Not At All Wrong</i>	<i>Wrong (Mean)</i>	<i>Easy</i>
71.24	5.75	5.31	4.87	11.06	1.77	2.65	4.25	90.70
Vignette Fairness: You see a politician make sure only supporters get access to jobs								
<i>Care</i>	<i>Fairness</i>	<i>Loyalty</i>	<i>Authority</i>	<i>Sanctity</i>	<i>Social Norms</i>	<i>Not At All Wrong</i>	<i>Wrong (Mean)</i>	<i>Easy</i>
6.28	75.78	8.97	6.28	1.35	1.35	0.90	4.24	90.09
Vignette Loyalty: You see a politician in your town say the neighboring town is better								
<i>Care</i>	<i>Fairness</i>	<i>Loyalty</i>	<i>Authority</i>	<i>Sanctity</i>	<i>Social Norms</i>	<i>Not At All Wrong</i>	<i>Wrong (Mean)</i>	<i>Easy</i>
11.21	5.83	52.47	8.07	2.24	20.18	20.63	2.45	82.43
Vignette Authority: You see a politician violating safety regulations ordered by the Chief of Police/Chief Constable at a disaster								

<i>Care</i>	<i>Fairness</i>	<i>Loyalty</i>	<i>Authority</i>	<i>Sanctity</i>	<i>Social Norms</i>	<i>Not At All Wrong</i>	<i>Wrong (Mean)</i>	<i>Easy</i>
18.40	8.96	6.60	55.66	2.83	7.55	3.77	3.86	83.02
Vignette Sanctity: You see a politician was found having sex with a teenager								
<i>Care</i>	<i>Fairness</i>	<i>Loyalty</i>	<i>Authority</i>	<i>Sanctity</i>	<i>Social Norms</i>	<i>Not At All Wrong</i>	<i>Wrong (Mean)</i>	<i>Easy</i>
19.64	3.57	3.57	7.59	63.39	2.23	2.23	4.45	86.92
Vignette Social Norm: You see a politician carrying briefing papers to the capitol/Houses of Parliament in a plastic grocery bag								
<i>Care</i>	<i>Fairness</i>	<i>Loyalty</i>	<i>Authority</i>	<i>Sanctity</i>	<i>Social Norms</i>	<i>Not At All Wrong</i>	<i>Wrong (Mean)</i>	<i>Easy</i>
9.38	3.57	5.80	14.73	8.48	58.04	45.98	1.99	74.32

Note: Numbers in Table are percentages. The category that scored the highest as to why the behaviour displayed in the vignette is considered wrong, is printed in bold. The variable Easy shows the percentage of respondents that can clearly imagine what happens in the vignette. The variable easy combines the response categories very easy and easy to imagine. The variable Not at all wrong indicates the percentage of respondents who considers the behaviour described in the vignette not at all wrong.

Table A4.2: Sample Demographics

Variable	
Male (in %)	58.74
Age (mean and standard deviation in brackets)	38.82 (.52)
White (in %)	73.51
Education (Bachelors degree or higher in %)	74.05
Democrat (in %)	55.86
Republican in %	33.69
Christian (in %)	54.23
Born Again Christian If Christian (in %)	52.49
Attendance Religious Services Once a Month or More (in %)	28.65

Note: N=555 For the Variable Born Again Christian N =301.

Table A4.3: Respondents Ratings of Vignettes

Scenario	Foundation	Care	Fairness	Loyalty	Authority	Sanctity	Social Norms	Not At All Wrong	Wrong (Mean)	Easy
You see a politician mocking an opponent when the opponent stutters during a debate*	Care	68.30	4.91	4.46	8.48	8.48	5.36	2.68	3.71	88.39
You see a politician say that an opponent is “too stupid to do the job”	Care	51.57	8.52	4.48	11.66	10.31	13.45	9.87	3.04	91.98
You see a politician step back when a severely burned constituent tries to shake hands	Care	59.29	7.52	7.96	7.52	6.64	11.06	3.54	3.35	90.71
You see a politician laugh out loud at a voter who asks for help	Care	62.83	8.41	8.41	6.64	9.29	4.42	4.42	3.80	86.22
You see a politician make fun of a constituent with mental health problems	Care	71.24	5.75	5.31	4.87	11.06	1.77	2.65	4.25	90.70
You see a politician make sure only supporters get access to jobs*	Fairness	6.28	75.78	8.97	6.28	1.35	1.35	0.90	4.24	90.09
You see a politician lying about credentials during the campaign	Fairness	4.41	67.40	7.49	7.49	7.49	5.73	2.20	4.14	92.48
You see a politician give a valuable contract to a company run by a family member	Fairness	5.53	69.59	9.68	5.07	4.61	5.53	4.61	3.79	88.94
You see a politician accepting help from foreign countries to win an election	Fairness	3.15	57.66	18.02	9.46	6.31	5.41	1.80	4.18	89.19
You see a politician providing needed help only to voters in the same political party	Fairness	11.82	62.27	14.09	4.09	2.27	5.45	6.36	3.66	94.09

You see a politician in your town say the neighboring town is better	Loyalty	11.21	5.83	52.47	8.07	2.24	20.18	20.63	2.45	82.43
You see a politician joke about the stupidity of Americans*	Loyalty	27.80	5.83	43.05	9.42	6.73	7.17	5.38	3.49	84.75
You see a politician refusing to sing the national anthem when others are singing it	Loyalty	5.45	4.55	28.18	41.82	4.55	15.45	20.00	2.80	82.19
You see a politician supporting another country's team at the Olympics	Loyalty	7.24	4.52	68.33	5.43	3.17	11.31	19.46	2.68	79.64
You see a politician violate the oath of office	Loyalty	7.52	26.11	23.89	34.96	4.42	3.10	2.21	4.16	88.50
You see a politician refuse to carry out a valid court order	Authority	5.56	35.19	5.09	43.52	6.02	4.63	3.24	3.58	88.43
You see a politician turn away and ignore the party leader*	Authority	10.16	4.81	32.09	41.71	4.81	6.42	15.00	2.67	87.67
You see a politician ignoring Constitutional requirements	Authority	4.11	35.16	5.02	48.86	4.57	2.28	0.91	4.40	89.95
You see a politician hunting where the town has posted no-hunting signs	Authority	10.67	22.67	6.22	49.78	3.56	7.11	3.56	3.90	93.27
You see a politician violating safety regulations ordered by the Chief of Police at a disaster	Authority	18.40	8.96	6.60	55.66	2.83	7.55	3.77	3.86	83.02
You see a politician was found having sex with a teenager	Sanctity	19.64	3.57	3.57	7.59	63.39	2.23	2.23	4.45	86.92
You see a politician watching videos of people having sex with animals	Sanctity	5.43	3.17	6.79	5.43	73.76	5.43	0.90	4.11	69.54
You see a politician getting drunk and vomiting at an official event	Sanctity	4.46	3.13	3.13	8.93	64.29	16.07	4.46	3.55	80.80

You see a politician leave the restroom without washing hands	Sanctity	7.76	3.20	5.48	2.74	61.64	19.18	9.59	3.01	90.41
You see a married politician is having extramarital homosexual relationships*	Sanctity	18.75	12.50	27.67	8.48	24.11	8.48	2.64	3.74	91.47
You see a politician wearing a dirty t-shirt and torn jeans at their own inauguration	Social Norms	6.25	5.80	4.91	42.86	22.32	17.86	15.63	2.91	73.66
You see a politician carrying briefing papers to the capitol in a plastic grocery bag	Social Norms	9.38	3.57	5.80	14.73	8.48	58.04	45.98	1.99	74.32
You see a politician eating tomato soup with a fork at a restaurant	Social Norms	0.0	2.29	3.67	11.93	8.26	73.85	59.17	1.77	71.88
You see a politician watching a sports event on a cell phone during a meeting	Social Norms	3.64	7.73	12.27	44.55	1.36	30.45	6.82	3.00	88.58
You see a politician celebrate after losing an election	Social Norms	7.27	4.09	18.64	9.09	4.55	56.36	40.00	2.07	60.00

*Note: N=555. The category that scored the highest as to why the behavior displayed in the vignette is considered wrong, is printed in bold. The variable Easy shows the percentage of respondents that can clearly imagine what happens in the vignette. The variable easy combines the response categories very easy and easy to imagine. The variable Not at all wrong indicates the percentage of respondents who considers the behaviour described in the vignette not at all wrong. *Moral violations vignettes selected for study.*

Appendix 4
Survey Experiment Questionnaire
(Questions Relevant to this Paper)

Q1 This is a study about how people respond to information about politicians, and your participation in the study is voluntary. If you decide to participate, you will answer questions about how you would feel if a politician exhibited certain behaviors. You will also be asked to provide some demographic information, such as your age and gender. You must be at least 18 years old and a US Citizen to participate in this study. The study should take approximately 10 minutes, and needs to be completed in a single session (without taking breaks). Participation in this study is voluntary. You may choose not to participate, and you may choose not to answer any questions with which you are not comfortable. You may also withdraw at any time during the study procedures, but unless you participate in the study until the end you will not receive payment for participation.

The research team and the Institutional Review Board (a committee that reviews research studies in order to safeguard the welfare of research participants) at the University of XXX are the only parties that will be allowed to see the data, except as required by law. If a report of this study is published, or the results are presented at a professional conference, only group results will be stated—the identity of individual participants will not be disclosed. All study data will be kept for at least three years.

There are only minimal risks associated with this study. You may be exposed to information about political policies or positions that you dislike or are uncomfortable with. You will receive payment for your time as specified by Dynada. You may also receive an indirect benefit by learning more about the thoughts and feelings you have in response to political candidates. Finally, there may be a general societal benefit in that we will learn more about responses to candidates and communications during political campaigns.

Do you wish to continue? Clicking "YES" will indicate your consent to use your responses in our study.

- Yes (1)
 - No (2)
-

Q2 First, we will ask some questions about you that will help us categorize your responses.
What is the highest level of school you have completed?

- High school diploma or equivalent (1)
- Some college, no degree (2)
- Associate degree (3)
- Bachelor's degree (4)
- Master's degree (5)
- Professional degree (J.D., M.B.A., M.D. or similar) (6)
- Doctoral degree (7)

Q3 What is your age?

Q4 What is your gender?

- Male (1)
- Female (2)
- Nonbinary (3)
- Other, please specify (4) _____

Q5 Please indicate your ethnicity or race. Check as many as apply to you.

- White (1)
- Hispanic or Latino (2)
- Black or African American (3)
- Native American or American Indian (4)
- Asian / Pacific Islander (5)
- Other, please specify (6) _____

Q6 Among the options below, which best describes your current religion?

- Buddhist (1)
 - Christian: Catholic (2)
 - Christian: Baptist (3)
 - Christian: Methodist (4)
 - Christian: Lutheran (5)
 - Christian: Latter Day Saints/Mormon (6)
 - Christian: Eastern Orthodox (7)
 - Christian: Other, please specify (8)
-

- Hindu (9)
 - Islam/Muslim (10)
 - Jewish (11)
 - No Particular Religion (12)
 - Spiritual, Not Religious (13)
 - Atheist (14)
 - Agnostic (15)
 - Other, please specify (16)
-

Display This Question:

If Q6 = Christian: Catholic

Or Q6 = Christian: Baptist

Or Q6 = Christian: Methodist

Or Q6 = Christian: Lutheran

Or Q6 = Christian: Latter Day Saints/Mormon

Or Q6 = Christian: Eastern Orthodox

Or Q6 = Christian: Other, please specify

Or Q6 = Other, please specify

Q7 Would you call yourself a born-again Christian, that is, have you personally had a conversion experience related to Jesus Christ?

Yes (1)

No (2)

Q8 How often do you attend religious services, apart from social obligations such as weddings or funerals?

Never (1)

Once a year or less (2)

A few times a year (3)

Once or twice a month (4)

Almost every week (5)

Every week or more than once a week (6)

Q8A What is your annual household income?

- Less than \$10,000 (1)
- \$10,000 - \$19,999 (2)
- \$20,000 - \$29,999 (3)
- \$30,000 - \$39,999 (4)
- \$40,000 - \$49,999 (5)
- \$50,000 - \$59,999 (6)
- \$60,000 - \$69,999 (7)
- \$70,000 - \$79,999 (8)
- \$80,000 - \$89,999 (9)
- \$90,000 - \$99,999 (10)
- \$100,000 - \$149,999 (11)
- More than \$150,000 (12)

Q9 What state do you currently live in?

RANDOMIZE – SELECT AND DISPLAY ONE VIGNETTE FROM Q10 – Q44

Q10 Next, we would like to have you consider an action by a politician that you might observe. Please read the statement very carefully and then answer the questions that follow it. When the arrow appears, click it to continue.

You see a Republican politician make fun of a constituent with mental health problems.

Q12 Next, we would like to have you consider an action by a politician that you might observe. Please read the statement very carefully and then answer the questions that follow it. When the arrow appears, click it to continue.

You see a Democratic politician make fun of a constituent with mental health problems.

Q14 Next, we would like to have you consider an action by a politician that you might observe. Please read the statement very carefully and then answer the questions that follow it. When the arrow appears, click it to continue.

You see a politician make fun of a constituent with mental health problems.

Q16 Next, we would like to have you consider an action by a politician that you might observe. Please read the statement very carefully and then answer the questions that follow it. When the arrow appears, click it to continue.

You see a Republican politician making sure only supporters get access to jobs.

Q18 Next, we would like to have you consider an action by a politician that you might observe. Please read the statement very carefully and then answer the questions that follow it. When the arrow appears, click it to continue.

You see a Democratic politician making sure only supporters get access to jobs.

Q20 Next, we would like to have you consider an action by a politician that you might observe. Please read the statement very carefully and then answer the questions that follow it. When the arrow appears, click it to continue.

You see a politician making sure only supporters get access to jobs.

Q22 Next, we would like to have you consider an action by a politician that you might observe. Please read the statement very carefully and then answer the questions that follow it. When the arrow appears, click it to continue.

You see a Republican politician in your town say the neighboring town is better.

Q24 Next, we would like to have you consider an action by a politician that you might observe. Please read the statement very carefully and then answer the questions that follow it. When the arrow appears, click it to continue.

You see a Democratic politician in your town say the neighboring town is better.

Q26 Next, we would like to have you consider an action by a politician that you might observe. Please read the statement very carefully and then answer the questions that follow it. When the arrow appears, click it to continue.

You see a politician in your town say the neighboring town is better.

Q28 Next, we would like to have you consider an action by a politician that you might observe. Please read the statement very carefully and then answer the questions that follow it. When the arrow appears, click it to continue.

You see a Republican politician violating safety regulations ordered by the Chief of Police at a disaster.

Q30 Next, we would like to have you consider an action by a politician that you might observe. Please read the statement very carefully and then answer the questions that follow it. When the arrow appears, click it to continue.

You see a Democratic politician violating safety regulations ordered by the Chief of Police at a disaster.

Q32 Next, we would like to have you consider an action by a politician that you might observe. Please read the statement very carefully and then answer the questions that follow it. When the arrow appears, click it to continue.

You see a politician violating safety regulations ordered by the Chief of Police at a disaster.

Q34 Next, we would like to have you consider an action by a politician that you might observe. Please read the statement very carefully and then answer the questions that follow it. When the arrow appears, click it to continue.

You see a Republican politician was found having sex with a teenager.

Q36 Next, we would like to have you consider an action by a politician that you might observe. Please read the statement very carefully and then answer the questions that follow it. When the arrow appears, click it to continue.

You see a Democratic politician was found having sex with a teenager.

Q38 Next, we would like to have you consider an action by a politician that you might observe. Please read the statement very carefully and then answer the questions that follow it. When the arrow appears, click it to continue.

You see a politician was found having sex with a teenager.

Q40 Next, we would like to have you consider an action by a politician that you might observe. Please read the statement very carefully and then answer the questions that follow it. When the arrow appears, click it to continue.

You see a Republican politician carrying briefing papers to the capitol in a plastic grocery bag.

Q42 Next, we would like to have you consider an action by a politician that you might observe. Please read the statement very carefully and then answer the questions that follow it. When the arrow appears, click it to continue.

You see a Democratic politician carrying briefing papers to the capitol in a plastic grocery bag.

Q44 Next, we would like to have you consider an action by a politician that you might observe. Please read the statement very carefully and then answer the questions that follow it. When the arrow appears, click it to continue.

You see a politician carrying briefing papers to the capitol in a plastic grocery bag.

Q49 When you think about this politician’s behavior, to what extent do you agree with the following statements? [RANDOMIZE ORDER OF ITEMS]

	Not at all (1)	Slightly (2)	Moderately (3)	Quite a bit (4)	Extremely (5)
The politician should apologize to the public for his/her behavior (Q49_ApolPublic)	☐				
The politician should restore the damage done by his/her behavior (Q49_Restore)	☐				
The politician should be removed from office because of his/her behavior (Q49_Remove)	☐				
The politician should receive a warning for his/her behavior from the party leader (Q49_Warn)	☐				
This politician should be reported to authorities because of his/her behavior (Q49_Report)	☐				
I would share a post about this politician’s behavior with my social network online (Q49_Share)	☐				
The politician should be forgiven for his/her behavior (Q49_Forgive)	☐				
I would report the politician for his/her behavior to authorities (Q49_I_Report)	☐				
The politician should apologize to all parties involved for his/her behavior (Q49_ApolParties)	☐				

Q51 Thinking about the behavior of the politician, how wrong is it?

- Not at all wrong (1)
- Not too wrong (2)
- Somewhat wrong (3)
- Very wrong (4)
- Extremely wrong (5)

Q50 What was the politician's party as described in the scenario?

- Republican (1)
- Democrat (2)
- Neither/No Party Listed (3)
- Do not know (4)

Q55 In general, how would you describe your political views?

- Very conservative (1)
- Conservative (2)
- Moderate (3)
- Liberal (4)
- Very liberal (5)

Q56 Generally speaking, do you usually think of yourself as a Republican, a Democrat, an Independent or what?

- Republican (1)
- Democrat (2)
- Independent (3)
- Something else (4)

Display This Question: If Q56 = Republican

Q57 Would you call yourself a strong Republican or not a very strong Republican?

- Strong (1)
- Not very strong (2)

Display This Question: If Q56 = Democrat

Q58 Would you call yourself a strong Democrat or not a very strong Democrat?

- Strong (1)
- Not very strong (2)

Display This Question: If Q56 = Independent

Q59 Do you think of yourself closer to the Republicans or the Democrats, or neither?

- Republican (1)
- Democrat (2)
- Neither (3)

Display This Question: If Q56 = Something else

Q60 Do you think of yourself closer to the Republicans or the Democrats, or Neither?

- Republican (1)
- Democrat (2)
- Neither (3)